

AUTISM IN CHILDREN: CAUSES, TYPES, SYMPTOMS AND RECOMMENDATIONS FOR PARENTS

Alimova Yu.B.

Academy of Nursing

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14916768>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 18th February 2025

Accepted: 23rd February 2025

Online: 24th February 2025

KEYWORDS

Autism, syndrome, stereotypic behavior, complex rehabilitation, corrective measures.

ABSTRACT

The article is devoted to the problems of early childhood autism, provides an overview of the main principles of effective intervention used in working with children, and provides examples of rehabilitation work with autistic children. The recommendations are universal and suitable for raising a child with spectrum disorders of any category.

АУТИЗМ У ДЕТЕЙ: ПРИЧИНЫ, ТИПЫ, СИМПТОМЫ И РЕКОМЕНДАЦИИ ДЛЯ РОДИТЕЛЕЙ

Алимова Ю.Б.

Академия сестринского дела

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14916768>

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Accepted: 23rd February 2025

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Аутизм, синдром, стереотипное поведение, комплексная реабилитация, коррекционные меры.

ABSTRACT

Статья посвящена проблемам раннего детского аутизма, содержит обзор основных принципов эффективного вмешательства, используемого в работе с детьми, и примеры реабилитационной работы с детьми-аутистами. Рекомендации универсальны и подходят для воспитания ребенка с расстройствами спектра любой категории.

BOLALARDA AUTIZM: SABABLARI, TURLARI, SIMPTOMLARI VA OTANALAR UCHUN TAVSIYALAR

Alimova Yu.B.

Hamshiralik akademiyasi

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14916768>

ARTICLE INFO

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Accepted: 23rd February 2025

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KEYWORDS

Autizm, sindrom, stereotipik xulq-atvor, kompleks rehabilitatsiya, tuzatish choralari.

ABSTRACT

Maqola erta bolalik autizmi muammolariga bag'ishlangan bo'lib, bolalar bilan ishlashda qo'llaniladigan samarali aralashuvning asosiy tamoyillariga sharh beriladi hamda autistik bolalar bilan rehabilitatsiya ishlarining namunalari keltiriladi. Tavsiyalar universal bo'lib, har qanday toifadagi spektr buzilishlariga ega bolalarni tarbiyalash uchun mos keladi.

Relevance of the problem: the article is devoted to the problem of autism in children, which is becoming especially relevant now, because the number of such children is increasing every year. Autistic individuals of all ages are ready to learn and embrace different levels of activity throughout their lives. However, data from many studies show that the work started at the right time gives the best results.

Autism (from the Greek word "autos" - "myself") is a disorder of mental and psychological development, in which the patient does not want to communicate with the outside world and the people around him. He likes solitude. He repeats the same behavior and words. A child diagnosed with autism lives in his own world. His thinking is different from others. Their actions are not related to reality. Emotional experiences play a key role in patients' actions. This syndrome is more common in boys than in girls. The variety of symptoms and the variability of the disease indicate the difficulty of this disease: from subtle autistic features to the need for constant care.

Reasons for the development of autism

Scientists cannot give a clear answer to the question of the causes of the appearance of this disease. The exact cause is unknown, indirect causes include:

- Genetic factor
- Heredity
- A combination of harmful effects on the mother's body during pregnancy and childbirth
- Diseases: meningitis, phenylketonuria, encephalitis
- mercury/lead poisoning
- late fatherhood or motherhood (after the age of 40).

Children with autism are born for a variety of reasons. And, as you can see, there are a lot of them. It is almost impossible to predict the birth of a baby with such a mental developmental disorder. In addition, there is a possibility that the predisposition to this disease will not be realized. But no one knows how to guarantee this with 100% certainty.

The main types of autism defined in the International Classification of diseases include:

- early childhood autism-"Kanner syndrome";
- atypical autism;
- Rett syndrome;
- Asperger syndrome.

Other very rare types of autism are classified under the heading "other types of autistic disorders".

Early childhood autism is a type of autism in which mental and behavioral disorders begin to manifest in the first days of a child's life. Instead of the term "early childhood autism" in medicine, "Kanner syndrome" is also used. This type of autism occurs in 10-15 children out of ten thousand babies and young children. Boys suffer from Kanner syndrome 3-4 times more often than girls. Symptoms of early childhood autism can appear in the first days of a baby's life. In such children, mothers note a disturbance in response to auditory stimuli and a delayed reaction to various visual communications. In the first years of life, children have difficulties in understanding speech. They also have delays in speech development. By age

five, a child with early childhood autism has persistent social interaction and behavior problems.

Atypical autism is a form of autism in which clinical manifestations may be hidden or mildly expressed for many years. In this disease, not all the main symptoms of autism are detected, which complicates the diagnosis at an early stage. The clinical presentation of atypical autism is expressed by different symptoms that may appear in different combinations in different patients. Characteristic groups of atypical autism symptoms: speech disorder; signs of emotional distress; signs of social adjustment and failure; thought disorder; nervousness.

Rett syndrome is a form of autism, in which severe psychoneurological disorders occur against the background of progressive degenerative changes in the central nervous system. Rett syndrome is caused by a mutation of one of the genes on the sex X chromosome. It only explains why girls get sick. Almost all male fetuses with one X chromosome in their genome die in utero. The first symptoms of the disease begin to appear 6-18 months after the birth of the child. Until then, the growth and development of the baby does not differ from the norm. Psychoneurological diseases develop in four stages of the disease. Due to severe motor disorders and obvious psychoneurological changes, Rett syndrome is the most severe form of autism and cannot be corrected.

Asperger syndrome is another type of autism. 80% of patients are boys. There are 7 cases of this syndrome per 1,000 children. Symptoms of the disease begin to appear at the age of 2-3 years, but the final diagnosis is often made at the age of 7-16 years. 3 main characteristics of Asperger's syndrome: social disorders; features of intellectual development; sensor (sensitivity) and motor disorders are observed.

Symptoms of autism in children

Early childhood autism is manifested as follows:

1. Symptoms of social skills disorder:

- lack of desire to communicate and interest in peers;
- ignoring the presence and feelings of people around;
- lack of imitative function, which is normal for the initial stage of development. Children

do not repeat the facial expressions of their parents, do not smile back, do not repeat the gestures of adults or do it consciously; children do not share their problems and thoughts with their parents.;

2. Problems in the development of speech and non-speech communication:

- lack of speech; lack of facial expressions and gestures;
- the child avoids eye contact, does not smile at the interlocutor;
- speech is developed, but the child does not communicate with others, does not respond to them;

• the child repeats phrases or individual words ("gramophone" or "parrot" speech according to Kanner's classification);

• phonetic disorders in speech. Autistics have problems with intonation, speech may be monotonous or rhythmically incorrect.;

3. Problems in the development of imagination, which are the cause of stereotypic behavior:

- nervous behavior;
- alienation;
- the child likes to play alone;
- lack of interest in inventing games, imaginary events;
- the child becomes attached to one toy or object and does not part with it, always tries to keep it in his hand;
- the child focuses on only one thing;

Autism manifests itself in children under 1 year of age and in the next two to three years of life.

How to treat? There is currently no specific treatment for autism. Unfortunately, there is no special pill or magic vaccine that can reliably protect the baby from the possible development of the disease. A single cause of the disease has not been identified. Lack of understanding of the root cause of the disease prevents scientists from developing a unique drug that can completely cure children with autism. The treatment of this mental illness is carried out in a complex manner, taking into account the symptoms that have arisen.

All treatment methods can be divided into several groups:

Medicines can be effective only to solve accompanying problems - aggressiveness, tics, anxiety, mood swings, hyperactivity and in other cases - antidepressants, antipsychotics; anticonvulsant drugs.

Psychological counseling. A child medical psychologist must work with a child with autism. Using various psychological methods, the specialist helps the child overcome anger and self-aggression, and also improves the inner feeling when integrating into a new group.

Today, *behavioral therapy* for autism, or *ABA*, is one of the most effective ways to treat childhood autism. It is based on the study of the influence of environmental factors on the behavior of an autistic person and the manipulation of these factors, behavioral technologies and training methods that allow to change it. The ABA method for autism has another name, which is "Behavior Modification". Behavioral therapy for autism according to the ABA program is based on the idea that any human behavior has certain consequences, and if the child likes it, he will repeat this behavior, and accordingly, if he does not like it, then he will not.

Speech therapy classes. Speech therapists should conduct training with a 3-year-old child. In such lessons, children learn to speak correctly and stop repeating words several times. Speech therapy classes help improve a child's vocabulary and add more words to their vocabulary. Such educational games help children better adapt to new groups and improve their social adjustment.

Sports are recommended for children. However, not all sports can be chosen. Quiet sports are more suitable for children with autism: learning to swim, playing chess or checkers, golf. It is worth choosing sports that require concentration on one object. It is best to avoid sports that require high speed or have a high risk of injury. Children with autism should not engage in running, jumping, boxing, or any form of strength wrestling. Team games are also not suitable. It is better to give preference to calmer sports that help strengthen the child's health and have a positive effect on his nervous system. Such children are very warm to various animals.

Praise as a treatment. Usually, therapy begins with teaching the child basic skills or appropriate behavior - for example, eye contact, learning to dress and put on shoes independently, proper feeding techniques, following simple vocal requests, where it is very important to constantly praise the little student. He needs to know that he will definitely praise good behavior. You can also think of rewards for your student in the form of a tasty dessert, a hug, a kiss, or a toy. With the right tactics, negative behavior will disappear.

Dangerous aspects

If autism is not treated in time, it can lead to the disruption of the patient's social and emotional ties with society.

Prevention

Unfortunately, there are no special methods for the primary prevention of this pathological condition. During pregnancy, women are advised to limit their intake of medication.

Recommendations for parents of an autistic child

Autistic children can appear capricious, manly, ill-mannered, sometimes very boring, unruly and rude. Misunderstanding and condemnation of others on the street, in transport, in the store significantly complicates the situation for him and his parents. As a result, such parents feel rejected, alone, they develop a fear of appearing in public with their child, and they begin to feel ashamed of their child. Sometimes children suffering from severe forms of autism are not admitted to any pre-school, and when they reach school age, they are recognized as "unfit for education" and not even admitted to a special school. Parents of such children feel especially unhappy. Living in such a nervous, stressful environment, sometimes feeling hopeless, some parents show their autistic child a state of depression - they shout at him, insult him and sometimes hit him. Experts say that a friendly environment in the family is important for successful remedial work with an autistic child. Therefore, it is very important for parents to create psychological comfort at home.

To establish a relationship with a child with autism, to be his friend and assistant, you should follow the following rules.

Rule 1: Get rid of your ambitions for your child. Do not make excessive demands on your child. In his life, he should fulfill his abilities, not your dreams.

Rule 2: Never be ashamed of your child. Recognize your child's right to be themselves. Take it as it is - with speechless speech and strange gestures.

Rule 3. When you want to teach a child something, do not expect quick results. There is no point in waiting for any results. Learn to enjoy even his small achievements. Little by little he learns everything, even little by little he demonstrates his knowledge. Be patient for many years.

Rule 4: When you look at your child, do not think about your own guilt. It is better to think that he is definitely not guilty of anything and that he needs you and your love for him.

Rule 5. The child does not demand sacrifices from you. By conforming to accepted popular stereotypes, you insist on sacrificing yourself. Although, of course, you will have to give up some things. But it is possible to find a way out of any, even the most difficult situation. And it depends only on you.

Parents should remember how difficult it is for their children to live in this world, learn to observe it patiently, notice and analyze every word and gesture out loud. It helps expand the inner world of an autistic child and encourages him to verbalize his thoughts, feelings and emotions. In addition, parents should know that their child is very vulnerable. Any word spoken by adults can cause an "emotional storm". Therefore, parents should be very careful and sensitive when communicating with their child.

Conclusion

Thus, autism is a general developmental disorder characterized by intolerance to normal human stress (everything is perceived too strongly and vividly), especially in close contact with another person, and a weak sense of self. At the same time, children with this diagnosis do not actually turn away from the world around them - their desire to communicate and understand is usually greater than that of normal children.

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